

A review of the genus *Crotalaria* L. (Crotalariaeae, Fabaceae)

Dr. Kiran Abasaheb More

Department & Research Institute in Botany,

Yashwantrao Chavan Arts & Science Mahavidyalaya Mangrulpir, Dist Wahim 444403

Mob - 9689081542

kmore1914@gmail.com

MS Received: 08.03.2025; MS Revised:08.04.2025; MS Accepted:09.04.2025)

MS 3394

(RESEARCH PAPER IN BOTANY,)

Abstract:

It is based on all the possible character and relevant data obtained from the study of various aspects of plants such as anatomy, ecology, embryology, phytochemistry, phytogeography, palynology etc. It not only implies the use of experimental procedures, but the taxonomic study of plants from the standpoint of population rather than individuals, and of the evolutionary processes which occur within populations. morphological and molecular data and reported global Infrageneric classification of the genus. She classified the species into eleven sections and raised some sub section of Polhill into sections due to non-monophyly. This system is the one currently in use. This further study shows following result.

Key words - *Crotalaria*, Review, Infrageneric classification, Molecular data, Morphology

Introduction

The family Fabaceae taxonomically comprises of three subfamilies which includes Ceasalpiniodeae, Mimosoideae and Papilionoideae. The family is considered to be more closely related to Connaraceae and Sapindaceae based on anatomy, morphology and biogeographical distributions (Polhill and Raven 1981). The emergence of the three subfamilies is based on the floral parts which include the size and symmetry of the flower, arrangement of petals in the flower bud, having united or free sepals, number of stamens, presence of pleogram, embryo radicle shape and presence of rood nodules (Lewis et al., 2005). Based on the differences in the above mentioned characteristics, it is believed that Mimosoideae and Papilionoideae are unique distinct lineage in the family which arose independently within a paraphyletic basal caesalpiniod assemblage (Polhill, 1994). Before the advent of family-wide molecular phylogenetic studies, Polhill (1994) in his last formal classification recognized 39 tribes, 670 genera and 16, 850 species within the family. After intensive research of more than 10 years in molecular phylogenetics studies of the family, the tribal and generic classification of the family has been updated which recognizes 36 tribes, 727 genera and 19, 327 species (Lewiz et al., 2005). The genera with 500 or more species within the family includes (Acacia, Astragalus, *Crotalaria* and Indigofera) and about 40 genera have 100 species or more, the family also contain nearly 500 genera that contain up to 10 species (Lewis et al., 2005). There has been disagreement on whether the family Fabaceae should be treated as one (composed of Ceasalpiniodeae, Mimosoideae and Papilionoideae) or each sub family should be treated as individual family, evidence from morphology and molecules support the legumes being one monophyletic family. This view has been supported by recent molecular phylogenetic studies (Doyle et al., 2000; Kajita et al., 2001; Wojciechowski, 2003; Wojciechowski et al., 2004) showing strong support for a monophyletic group that is more closely related to Polygalaceae, Surianaceae and Quillajaceae, which together form the order Fabaes (Sensu Angiosperm Phylogeny Group, 2003)

Results And Discussion**Taxonomic History Of The Genus *Crotalaria***

Carolus Linnaeus was the first to described the genus *Crotalaria*, he named 13 species in his Species Plantarum of 1753 which are *Crotalaria perfoliata* L., *C. sagitalis* L., *C. juncea* L., *C. triflora* L., *C. villosa* L., *C. verrucosa* L., *C. lotifolia* L., *C. lunaris* L., *C. laburnifolia* L., *C. micans* L., *C. albanand* L. *C. quinquefolia* L. (Linnaeus 1753). The number of the species within the genus increased to 37 (Lamarck, 1786). De Candolle (1825) reported 137 species. Thereafter the numbers increased to the total of 700 species that is accounted for at present (Le Roux et al., 2013). The genus is listed as one of the fifty largest seed plant genera (Mabberley, 2008). Detailed review of African species was given by (Baker, 1914), He revised and described 309 species in the continent. The most extensive study in the history of *Crotalaria* taxonomy was by (Polhill 1982), he conducted a thorough taxonomic revision on species in Africa and Madagascar where he

reported 511 species. In Africa Thunberg (1823), reported 11 species from the Cape, South Africa. Similarly Harvey (1862) described 24 new species from the same region, which are now seen in other part of Africa (Le Roux et al., 2013). 21 species are enumerated from region of Empire of Ethiopia which comprises of Southern Egypt, Eastern Sudan, Yemen and Western Saudi Arabia by (Richard 1847). Verdoorn (1928) published a taxonomic revision of the genus where he recognized and reported 124 species in Southern Africa and South Tropical Africa, excluding Angola. Baker (1876) in his work on the genus in Tropical Africa, he treated 106 species. 24 species were collected in East Africa by Hildebrand and their description was published by (Vatke 1879). 24 years later, Taubert (1893) increases West African species to 56 in his publication. Milne Redhead (1961) and polhil (1968, 1976) conduct an in depth studies and revised the species within the genus in East Tropical Africa and reported 199 species in the area, 56 species from the same region were also published by (Taubert 1895). In Angola 62 new species were described by (Wilczek, 1953a), he also revised 189 species from the same country (Wilczek, 1953b). Hepper (1958) revised the species of West Africa and reported 51 species and Da Torre (1960) described 36 new species and revised 138 species (1962) from the region, 26 species were treated in Namibia. In Ethiopia 85 species were treated (Thulin, 1983) similarly he reported enumerated 39 species in Somalia (Thulin, 1989). Du Puy and Labat (2002) conducted a research on Madagascar species and enumerated 53 species. Roy and Sharon (2005) described and illustrated new species of the genus *Crotalaria mwangulangoi* from the Udzungwq Mountains, Tanzania. Two new species of *Crotalaria*, *C. cupricola* Leteinturier and *C. serpenticola* Leteinturier are reported from metallifeorus sites in Zimbabwe by (Leteinturier and Polhill 2003). A new species known as *Crotalaria arrecta* Hemp and Polhill was reported from Kenya, the species was previously.

IV. INFRAGENERIC CLASSIFICATION The first infrageneric classification of the species within the genus was given by (Lamarck 1786), he divided the genus into two groups which are simple leaved group and trifoliolate, digitate leaved group. Wight and Walker-Arnott (1834) used reproductive characters and reported 13 sub divisions with the two groups reported by Lamarck. Bentham (1843) used leaf shape and divided the genus into two groups which are simple leaved and trifoliolate leaved, he further divided the simple leaved into seven sections and trifoliolate leaved into 11 sections, this classification is similar to (Wight and Walker-Arnott 1834). Harvey (1862) maintained the simple leaved group and divides the species within the trifoliolate group into Oliganthe and Racemosae, based on number of flower per raceme, thereby dividing the genus into three sections. Baker (1876) followed Harvey system of classification and adopts it but used fruit shape, flower arrangement and excluded Racemosae and create four additional groups (Chrysocalycinae, Sphaerocarpaceae, Oocarpae and Cylindrocarpaceae). Four sections were created based on leaf character (Simplicifoliae, Unifoliolatae, Trifoliolatae and Multifoliolatae) by (Taubert 1893) following Bentham's classification. He also used

vegetative and reproductive morphological characters to further divide the *Simplicifoliae* into seven series and *Trifoliolatae* into ten series. Baker (1914) adopted previous sections *Simplicifoliae*, *Sphaerocarpaceae* and *Chrysocalycinae* reported by (Baker 1876) and created three additional new sections and five subsections, the sections are *Spinosae*, *Farctae* and *Eucrotalaria* and the subsections are (*Grandiflorae*, *Mediocriflorae*, *Oliganthae*, *Parviflorae* and *Stipulosae*). Harms (1915), Senn (1939) and Peltier (1959) adopted the previous system of classification which was based on leaf, but Harms (1917) modified the section *Chrysocalycinae*. He removed *C. niginas* from the section and placed it in the newly created section *Tetralobocalyx* Harms. Wilczek (1953b) is not satisfied with using leaf as a tool for sectional classification because some species have both unifoliolate and trifoliolate leaves, therefore he disagreed with previous classification systems. He erected seven groups using petiole length, presence or absence of stipules and their size, which he named the groups "Group I-VII". Polhill (1968) is not satisfied with any of the classification systems, and he also reported the difficulty of infrageneric classification of the species within the genus. He gave an account of the history and development of the classification systems for African Species (Polhill, 1968). He used a combination of flower morphology, legume and bracteole shape and divided the genus into 11 sections and seven sub sections. Bisby (1970, 1973) included 273 species and 52 characters that are similar to those used by Polhill (1968) which include floral characters, habit and stipule characters and conducted taximetric analyses. His findings were similar to that of Polhill's (1968) classification system. Data from Polhill (1968) and Bisby (1973) were combined for the infrageneric classification system and found some discrepancies that were re-evaluates (Bisby and Polhill, 1973). Their finding resulted to an improved classification system (Bisby and Polhill, 1973; Polhill, 1982) which comprised of eight sections and nine subsections. The sections are: *Grandiflorae*, *Chrysocalycinae*, *Incanae*, *Stipulosae*, *Hedriocarpaceae*, *Geniculatae*, *Schizostigma*, *Calycinae*, and *Crotalaria*.

Ansari (2008) used modified infrageneric classification system of (Wight and Walker-Arnott, 1834; Bentham, 1843 and Baker 1876) which are based on leaf and revised the taxonomy of Indian species. In his publication Ansari (2002) he reported nine sections and six subsections; which are not formally described. He considered Polhill's classification system and updated his previous system of 2002 using the same sections as Polhill (1982), but listed only sections that are in India and included six sections and 12 subsections (Ansari, 2006, 2008). In his work he recognized four subsection within section *Calycinae* and four subsection within the section *Crotalaria* Le Roux et al., (2013) proposed sectional classification system for the entire genus for the first time based on morphological and morphometric studies and phylogenetic approach. Her new system comprises of eleven sections: *Amphitrichae*, *Calycinae*, *Crotalaria*, *Geniculatae*, *Glaucuae*, *Grandiflorae*, *Hedriocarpaceae*, *Incanae*, *Schizostigma*, *Borealigeniculatae* and *Stipulosae*. She modified *Geniculatae*, *Calycinae* and *Crotalaria* sections. The subsections *Stipulosae*, *Glaucuae* and *Incanae* are raised to sectional level, while some groups previously recognized as subsections are abandoned due to non-monophyly (subsection *Chrysocalycinae*, *Hedriocarpaceae*, *Macrostachyae* and *Tetralobocalyx*). Two new sections are recognized, *Amphitrichae* and *Borealigeniculatae* V. ECONOMIC

IMPORTANCE OF CROTALARIA *Crotalaria* species are annual shrubs very useful in agriculture (Magingo, 1992), as green manure and cover plants in plantations. They are also used as a source of diet for livestock. Many of the species are known to be nodulated with soil *Rhizobia* (Allen and Allen 1981, Faria et al., 1989) and they are also good in fixing atmospheric nitrogen. Sustainable crop production is achieved through the management of soil fertility and cover crops play a key role in soil fertility through a reduction in synthetic nutrients applied. Legumes are effective in the fixation of nitrogen and can accumulate large amounts of biomass that help to increase the nutrient availability and organic matter in the soil. Some of the long term

benefits obtained from the use of cover crops include weed suppression through competition or allelopathy and possible insect control (Phatak et al., 2002). While some species of *Crotalaria* are poisonous, others like *C. retusa*, *C. micronata*, *C. falcata* and *C. vogelii* remain some of the important fodder plants for cattle and small ruminants. (Nuhu et al., 2000) also reported that *Crotalaria* species are widely used in Zaria, Nigeria in feeding of sheep and cattle. *Crotalaria* species are widely used in veterinary pharmacy in preventing liver disease (Nwude and Ibrahim, 1980, Nuhu, 1999). In Tanzania *Crotalaria comosa* Bak provides nitrogen to the crops intercropped with and assist in the control of weeds and nematodes (Mukurasi, 1986). The species within the genus like *Crotalaria recta* L. are used as food source by larvae of *Lepidoptera* species, the insect also used the plant as defense against their predators (Thomas 2003). Cook and White (1996) revealed that *C. retusa* L. seeds as source of fibres, silage and green manure when removed from pods by pounding. According to Akintayo, (1997) oils derived from *Crotalaria bongensis* Bak, *C. naragutensis* Hutch and *C. lachnophora* Desu. Seeds are not suitable for use as edible oil and soap production but many however, are useful for the production of paint and shampoos. *Crotalaria* is also used in the treatment of diabetics (Pullaiah and Chandrasukha, 2008), skin infection, snake bit and stomach ache prevention (Verdhana, 2008).

Economic Importance Of Crotalaria

Crotalaria species are annual shrubs very useful in agriculture (Magingo, 1992), as green manure and cover plants in plantations. They are also used as a source of diet for livestock. Many of the species are known to be nodulated with soil *Rhizobia* (Allen and Allen 1981, Faria et al., 1989) and they are also good in fixing atmospheric nitrogen. Sustainable crop production is achieved through the management of soil fertility and cover crops play a key role in soil fertility through a reduction in synthetic nutrients applied. Legumes are effective in the fixation of nitrogen and can accumulate large amounts of biomass that help to increase the nutrient availability and organic matter in the soil. Some of the long term benefits obtained from the use of cover crops include weed suppression through competition or allelopathy and possible insect control (Phatak et al., 2002). While some species of *Crotalaria* are poisonous, others like *C. retusa*, *C. micronata*, *C. falcata* and *C. vogelii* remain some of the important fodder plants for cattle and small ruminants. (Nuhu et al., 2000) also reported that *Crotalaria* species are widely used in Zaria, Nigeria in feeding of sheep and cattle. *Crotalaria* species are widely used in veterinary pharmacy in preventing liver disease (Nwude and Ibrahim, 1980, Nuhu, 1999). In Tanzania *Crotalaria comosa* Bak provides nitrogen to the crops intercropped with and assist in the control of weeds and nematodes (Mukurasi, 1986). The species within the genus like *Crotalaria recta* L. are used as food source by larvae of *Lepidoptera* species, the insect also used the plant as defense against their predators (Thomas 2003). Cook and White (1996) revealed that *C. retusa* L. seeds as source of fibres, silage and green manure when removed from pods by pounding. According to Akintayo, (1997) oils derived from *Crotalaria bongensis* Bak, *C. naragutensis* Hutch and *C. Table 1-* Histochemical color reactions of *E. laciniata panigrahi* leaf powder.

Acknowledgement

I will thankful to provide space and assistance needed for the study, the management of Shri Shivaji Mahavidyalaya Parbhani, & Yashwantrao Chavan Arts and Science Mahavidyalaya Mangrulpir, District Washim. for further remaining investigation of *Crotalaria*.

References

1. **Annapura A and Hatware K, 2014.** Effect of aqueous extract of *Euphorbia heterophylla* on blood glucose levels of alloxan induced diabetic rats. *International Journal of Research in Pharmacy and Chemistry*, 4(3), 669-672.
2. **Andreia, S. F. and Ana M. G. de A. T. (2005).** A new species of *Crotalaria* (Leguminosae, Papilionoideae) from Southeastern Brazil. *Novon* 15(3): 418-420.
3. **Bentham, G. (1843).** Enumeration of the Leguminosae indigenous to southern Asia and central and southern Africa

- XV. *Crotalaria*. London Journal of Botany 2: 472–481, 559–593.
4. **Crisp, M.D., Gilmore, S. and Van Wyk, B.E. (2000).** Molecular phylogenetics of the genistoid tribes of papilionoid legumes. In: P.S. Herendeen and A. Brubeau (ed), *Advances in Legume Systematics*. Kew: Royal Botanical Gardens. Vol. 9. pp. 249-276
 5. **Falodun A, Okunrobo LO and Uzoamaka N, 2006.** Phytochemical screening and anti-inflammatory evaluation of methanolic and aqueous extracts of *Euphorbia heterophylla* Linn (Euphorbiaceae). *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 5(6):529-531.
 6. **Hepper, F.N. (1958).** Papilionaceae, *Crotalaria*. In: R.W.J. Keay (ed), *Flora of West Africa*. London: Crown Agents, pp.544-553.
 7. **James O and Friday ET, 2010.** Phytochemical composition, bioactivity and wound healing potential of *Euphorbia heterophylla* (Euphorbiaceae) leaf extract. *International Journal on Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Research*, 1(1), 54-63.
 8. **Khory, R.N. and Katrak, N.N.(1984).** *Materia medica of India and their therapeutics*. Neeraj Publishing House, Delhi.
 9. **Nakata PA, 2003.** Advances in our understanding of calcium oxalate crystal formation and function in plants. *Plant Science*, 164(6):901-909.
 10. **Neinhuis C, Barthlott W, 1997.** Characterization and distribution of water-repellent, self-cleaning plant surfaces. *Annals of botany*, 79(6):667-677.
 11. **Metcalf R and Chalk L, 1988.** *Anatomy of dicotyledons*. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 2nd ed. 1, 276.
 12. **Riederer M and Schreiber L, 2001.** Protecting against water loss: analysis of the barrier properties of plant cuticles. *Journal of experimental botany*, 52(363):2023-32.
 13. **Pullaiah, T.C. and Chandrasukha, N.K. (2008).** *Antidiabetic plants in India and herbal based research*. New Delhi: Regency publication, 125p.
 14. **Rodriguez E, Towers GH and Mitchell JC, 1976.** Biological activities of sesquiterpene lactones. *Phytochemistry*. 15(11):1573-80.
 15. **Sankatha Prasad Sigh,(1978)** Structure and development of seeds in *Euphorbia geniculata* orteg
 16. **Sundareasan, V.; De Britto A. J.(1999)** (Department of Botany, St.xavier's (Autonomous)preliminary phytochemical studies on some mdicinal plants of Tirunelveli hills. *journal of Economic and Taconomic Botany*, v-23(2): p. 377-380,
 17. **Ughachukwu PO, Ezenyeaku CCT, Onwurah WO, Ifediata FE, Ogamba JO and Afonne OJ, 2013.** Effect on some haematological indices of human whole blood when aqueous leaf extract of *Euphorbia heterophylla* was used as storage anticoagulant. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 12(31), 4952-4955.
 18. **Wallis TE, 1985.** *Textbook of Pharmacognosy*. Published by SK Jain
 19. **Williams CA, Houlst JR, Harborne JB, Greenham J and Eagles J, 1995.** A biologically active lipophilic flavonol from *Tanacetum parthenium*. *Phytochemistry*, 38(1):267-70.
 20. **Woodward FI, 1998.** Do plants really need stomata? *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 1:471- 80.
 21. **Zimmermann, M.H. and Ayodeji, J. (1981).** Vesel length distribution in stems of some American Woody Plants. *Can. J. Bot.*,59: 1882-1892.